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Summary

Tbilisi declaration defines environmental education (EE) as a learning process to gain knowledge on environment and its challenges, to develop the skills to address those challenges and impart behavioral change towards informed decision and responsible action. Inspired from nature observation and appreciation of the functioning of environment, EE has always necessitated the need of field observational skills and analytical thought processing for comprehending the intricate mechanism and complex interaction of environment and its associative challenges. This makes the field observation and hands on practical learning as major components in environmental education. So any enhancements in these two components would significantly improve the efficacy and goal of EE.

In par with objective of the National council for Science and Technology communication, Rajat Jayanti Vigyan Sancharak Fellowship, the current project is of application oriented education technology development research. The aim of the project is to explore the role of new generation tools such as location based augmented reality games, participatory sensing and simulation as applications for Environmental Education. The prime objective of the project is to develop a location based augmented reality games as an environmental education tool to be field tested in the thorny forests of 55 acre SACON campus. The main research question is related with how far the game can augment the environmental education and current practices in nature education trails. What design part attributes to the better playability and learning experience in ARG.

In this line, we developed a location based augmented reality game named 'Taxosearch'. Its main aim is to impart encouragement and learning to improvise plant identification skills among users. It has the functionality of location based quizzes in hand held tablet computers augmented with environmental observation and search queries. In participatory sensing domain, a activity module named 'Nudge' was developed focusing on developing functionality in hand held tablet computers with low cost dust monitoring sensors. This can address the need of tools for field activity in learning about particulate matter pollution and other environmental pollution problems in urban spaces. For participatory simulation domain, a virtual globe based simulation game 'Chipko wetlands' was designed and presented in a on-line community forum for further review and development.

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Contents

Summary	i
Acknowledgements	ii
List of Figures	v
List of Tables	vi
1 Taxosearch: a location based augmented reality game for improving plant identification skills	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Background	4
1.3 Game Overview	4
1.4 Game Code	5
1.5 Taxosearch: Features and program	5
1.5.1 Feature overview	5
1.5.2 Features	6
1.5.3 Program overview	6
1.5.4 Program packages and classes: Map application	6
1.5.4.1 Base map	6
1.5.4.2 Map overlay	14
1.5.5 Program packages and classes: quiz application	15
1.6 Conclusion	15
2 Nudge: A participatory sensing based field activity for learning about particulate matter pollution in urban spaces	16
2.1 Introduction	16
2.2 Background	17
2.3 Activity Overview	17
2.4 Activity code	17
2.5 Nudge: Features and program	18
2.5.1 Feature overview	18
2.5.2 Features	18
2.5.3 Program	18
2.6 Conclusion	23

A Chipko wetlands (Hug the wetlands)- a game for adaptation thinking in urban area -proposal	24
A.1 Introduction	24
A.2 Game overview	25
A.3 Development feasibility	26
A.4 Expected Outcomes	27
Bibliography	29

List of Figures

1.1	Taxosearch:Overview	6
1.2	Taxosearch:welcome screen	7
1.3	Taxosearch:Location map	7
1.4	Taxosearch:Tree number	8
1.5	Taxosearch:reality augmentation	8
1.6	Taxosearch:AR question	9
1.7	Taxosearch: Plant Info search question	9
1.8	Kiwix:content	10
1.9	Kiwix:Article	10
1.10	Taxosearch:Sound based quiz	11
1.11	Taxosearch: Sound based quiz interface	11
1.12	Taxosearch:Image based quiz	12
1.13	Taxosearch: Image based quiz interface	12
1.14	Taxosearch: Feedback	13
1.15	Taxosearch:Program Overview	13
1.16	Base map application packages	14
1.17	Map overlay application packages	14
1.18	Quiz application packages	15
2.1	Nudge:Overview	18
2.2	Nudge:Android based dust sensing device	19
2.3	Nudge>Data communcation and dust reading	19
A.1	Chipko wetlands: game steps	25

List of Tables

2.1	Particulars used in Android tablet based dust sensing device	19
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Chapter 1

Taxosearch: a location based augmented reality game for improving plant identification skills

1.1 Introduction

Taxonomy plays a major role in understanding the nature and its system through its descriptiveness and systematic organization of the nature components [1]. It greatly helps in sustainable usage and informed interaction by human society towards nature and its resources. Historically the practice of taxonomy has great implication to our society starting from medicinally important plants' description in *De Materia Medica* by Dioscorides of 1st century to 10th century agriculture taxonomy work of Ibn Washiya in *Al Filaha Nabatiya* and to 17th century seminal work of Carl Linnaeus's *Systema Naturae*[2]. All these works largely facilitated the identification of plants or other living organisms for societal beneficial usage through diagrammatic and verbal description. In modern day's field guides comprising of pictorial and verbal dichotomous description of the organisms were the major way for lowest possible taxonomic class identification of organisms. In environmental education, knowledge and expertise in taxonomy is set to be an important skill set. It encourages the environmental observation and apprehension of importance of living organisms to the functioning of the ecosystem[3]. Though field guides are largely used, it has severe drawbacks in case of user friendliness and the huge learning curve and other technical difficulties of taxonomic description. It is quite visible for the case of even experts / professional [4]. These drawbacks has severely deterred

the involvement of amateur and encouragement to young people for a taxonomy profession and created a huge knowledge gap in application of taxonomy in environmental protection and biodiversity conservation.

Developments in computer vision, image processing, and other computational technology are largely considered as important solutions for this. Automatic photograph recognition, image and sound processing for identifying the plant or other living organisms have increasingly started to be in use for taxonomic species level identification especially for floral groups[4], [5]. To a great extent, these tools help in alleviating the intrinsic difficulties of manual dichotomous key and field guide based identification which is tiresome and time consuming[6]. However, the intrinsic limitations in such technology largely prohibit wide adoption of these tools in the field especially because of higher error prone and development cost. The human vision based identification named as Mechanical Turk was increasingly used in these cases where the capability of human pattern identification is used for complex pattern recognition[7]. It is also used for attribute deduction during the pattern identification process; however, it has very limited functionality using the technological intervention because such interventions need to grow much more intricate and responsive to simulate human pattern identification.

The computational tools developed for this cause, especially based on hand held computers or mobile phone, has great role in developing the Augmented Reality Game (ARG) related with Taxonomy. The term augmented reality indicates enhancement of user perception about reality with computer assistance[8]. The processes of augmentation are initiated by the aid of input modes which can be recognized by the computer program such as motion, sound or location specificity (GPS coordinates). This initiation results in presentation of information about the real world element or simulation about the element's dynamics. The advantages of ARGs, as generally with games[9], in terms of providing challenge, fun, and long lasting interest with educative platform can be significantly used in the cause of popularizing taxonomic skill for environmental observation / education. Aim of the game Taxosearch is to encourage learning taxonomic skill using the simple dichotomous quiz based attribute identification of plant species. For that, it uses a search engine based plant identification process.

The Internet search engines have changed the landscape of information access. Using a set of key words to search for indexed stored information, it facilitate to narrow down the task of information retrieval to the most specific content the user is querying for. This has generated far-reaching implication in usage and production of information in day-to-day life of common public[10]. The greater of the significances can be seen in educational sector especially in individual learning of simple to sophisticated skills. In this aspect, the process of learning to do some task of day-to-day life has considerably

simplified. The developments in search engine technology have far advanced to provide even semantic search results where the results are modified intelligently to the users' requirements. These developments have necessitated a new set of skills to use optimally the search engines[11]. The computer becoming more and more hand-held the process of information retrieval through search engines has become largely ubiquitous in real life applications. Search engines have immense applications in the field identification of living organisms. The ever-increasing availability of indexed, tagged meta and location information of organisms with their taxonomical identity paves a simplified way for learning the skill of identifying living organisms. The increasingly being digitized scientific field of taxonomy is immensely simplifying the tedious processes of field identification of plant species. The point has reached where in with some knowledge on various parts of organism, which are easily observable or recognizable, as keywords, it is very much easy to for species level identification of organisms, in the present case tree species. In environmental education, the identification of common living organisms for better comprehension of its role and importance in ecosystems is important skill[3]. The development of this skill in Internet age needs to be sharpened and has to be associated with advantages of search engine setups.

The augmented reality game Taxosearch is intended to provide a similar field based platform of acquiring the plant identification skill for a search engine based Internet age Taxonomy. The main aim of the game is two fold; one is to impart the necessary skills, encouragement to acquire plant identification skills. Second one is related with improving the observational skill among players on environmental monitoring in terms of recognizes the various ecological cycles. As a field based observation quiz game, the objective of the game is related with plant parts recognition, relating it with commonly used terms of taxonomy, nomenclature of the plant species, evolutionary lineage identification and recognition of ecological cycle on the plant. It basically improves the plant identification skill among the players in terms of

- Plant part recognition, which helps to differentiate the parts of organisms and found the underlying structural pattern in it
- Plant morphological / taxonomic term recognition which helps to identify the parts of a plant and used for search query
- Skills related with nomenclature, taxonomic systematic name its relation with common vernacular names with real world correlation which helps in understanding / appreciating the nomenclature practices behind plant naming

- Skills related with classification, evolutionary lineage, choose the correct pedigree tree which is helpful in appreciating the evolutionary significance and system interrelationship,
- Skills related with environmental monitoring to observe the characters of plant and rationalize the character with various penology and prevailing environmental condition.

1.2 Background

The related work carried out in the aspect of taxonomy most specifically fall under two categories of automatic or manual pattern identification. In the case of augmented reality field guides, AR museum guides are increasingly used as field guides. Though it is not working as game it provides the rich multimedia content about the museum specimen using the AR location based information [12]. In the case of automatic taxonomy field guides, leaf snap is one of the well developed and most successful algorithms in identifying the plants up to species level [4]. The database of this iPhone based application currently covers 143 trees from New York State of USA. Based on the computer vision technology, the algorithm used in the application identifies the shape of the leaf which was photographed. Based on the classification and pattern recognition techniques, the software suggest the number of most correct plant species from the leaf structure and gives more information content on other parts of plant species to initiate the correct identification of the plant species. The leaf snap application also provides an associated game related to the automatic plant species identification. In the case of full-fledged game related with taxonomy the game ‘Find the odd leaf’ recognize the need of human interventions in computational pattern recognition [13]. The game asks, in a web based game platform, player to identity odd leaf pattern from a set of six leaf pictures with correct identification fetch points for players. The game ‘pocket plant guide’ gives similar experience with field experience [14] and in a semi ARG setup it asks the players to identify the six indicator species in the real field to understand vegetation succession pattern.

1.3 Game Overview

The game play revolves around identifying the plant species by observing it in the field. The identification will be carried out by a multiple choice quiz format in Tablet. The design of the quiz is in such a way that it necessitates field observation, referring the

observation with offline search engine/wikipedia article to get the answer. Covering more number of plant identification the player gets more points in the game.

1.4 Game Code

The game is written in Android using Eclipse. The game basically uses open source code of two android applications namely Fuchs map [15] and Chuck quiz [16] game android apps. The complete source code of the game which is in open source domain is hosted in <https://github.com/nishadhka/Taxosearch>. Full source code of this game can be downloaded from this link.

1.5 Taxosearch: Features and program

1.5.1 Feature overview

The game starts from a off-line location map of SACON campus (Fig.1.1), in which trees selected for quiz is marked with point overlay in map. By selecting the point marker player can view it AR number. To start the game, player has to physically go near to the marked tree. High resolution satellite imagery based off-line map in application helps in guiding player to reach near to the marked tree. By entering tree number in Augmented reality screen, it shows leaf image of the selected tree to find by player. Completion of this task makes player to enter into quiz section. The quiz section comprised of multiple choice question types instigative of off-line ‘Wikipedia’ search, observation, sound and image based questions. The feedback is given in terms of time taken to answer as well as the correctness of the answers. Following section shows images (Figs.1.2 to 1.14) of the features in Taxosearch.

FIGURE 1.1: Overview of the features available in Taxosearch game

1.5.2 Features

1.5.3 Program overview

The game comprised of a Android offline map [15] and a quiz template application [16]. The whole program is written in Java using eclipse for 'Android' . It is grouped into maps and quiz sub applications with number of programming packages in each of them 1.15. Each of the packages are comprised of java classes with specific functionalities (Figs.1.16 and 1.17).

1.5.4 Program packages and classes: Map application

1.5.4.1 Base map

The packages included in this group create a base map of game location. The base map imageries are downloaded from Mobile Atlas creator software as Rmaps sqlite data base file. The classes in the package visualize the base map from data base and enables touch and drag options.

FIGURE 1.2: Welcome screen of the Taxosearch game

FIGURE 1.3: SACON campus map with available location based quizzes positions in green pointer

FIGURE 1.4: Touching on green pointer reveals tree number near to player's locality

FIGURE 1.5: Reality augmentation screen with facility to enter tree number

FIGURE 1.6: Augmented reality question asks to locate pictured leaf bearing tree in player's current locality

FIGURE 1.7: A quiz question asks to find information from off-line Wikipedia in tablet computer

FIGURE 1.8: Content page of Off-line Wikipedia application, Kiwix

FIGURE 1.9: Article page of Off-line Wikipedia application, Kiwix

FIGURE 1.10: Song based question

FIGURE 1.11: Facility to hear sound

FIGURE 1.12: Image based question

FIGURE 1.13: Facility to view image

FIGURE 1.14: Final screen of the game with time and answer correctness based feedback

FIGURE 1.15: Overview of programs in Taxosearch game

FIGURE 1.16: Taxosearch map application data base helper package

1.5.4.2 Map overlay

This classes gives functionality to overlay markers in base map defined by particular location with its latitude and longitudinal information. Enables to select and view the particular tree number marked as a pointer in the base map. Map application was customized to include augmented reality quizzes and imageries for the game.

FIGURE 1.17: Taxosearch map application data base helper package

1.5.5 Program packages and classes: quiz application

Base quiz application was customized with time tracking facility, image and sound based quizzes. The quiz application is based on sqlite data base. The packages involves classes to convert the sqlite entries into question and answer choices. This is further record for time tracking and correctness of the quizzes.

FIGURE 1.18: Taxosearch map application data base helper package

1.6 Conclusion

A playable location based augmented reality game Taxosearch was developed. The objective of the Rajat Jayanti Vigyan Sancharak Fellowship to better communicate the science can be achieved by successful implementation of this game and continuous usage in the nature field trails and other environmental education related activities.

Chapter 2

Nudge: A participatory sensing based field activity for learning about particulate matter pollution in urban spaces

2.1 Introduction

Environmental education aims to improve the knowledge and awareness about environment, its associative challenges, and develops skills to address those challenges and motivate to take informed decision and responsible action among the learners (UNESCO, Tbilisi Declaration, 1978)[3]. Thus inculcating the understanding of environmental issues complexity, its multi-component interrelationships and uncertain trajectories with motivation to take part and take corrective actions are important in achieving the aims of environmental education. In general these needs were felt as basic skills to be acquired in overall educational perspective in 21st century [17]. It is generally aimed to acquire skills to deal with knowledge based economy and society which would require to work with incomplete or scattered information, adapt to changing conditions, manage complexity, and instantly creating and sharing the knowledge. In this context education based on participatory experience-based learning provides moderately authentic or real life experience of solving problems [8]. Enriched with appropriate tools, intellectual processes, motivations and experience of science practice in problem solving, it can give the essential ingredient for achieving objectives of environmental education[3, 10].

Recent developments in computer technology, in wider prevalence of computing and Internet resources, compactness and ubiquitousness of those resources with location-aware systems are providing basic resources for participatory experience based learning. The wide popularity of Arduino micro controller with its characteristics of easy provision to develop sensing and actuator systems becoming widely felt as important tool in educational technology [18]. This provisioning of sensing systems enables common public to enquire about their environment scientifically. Which enables to addresses the growing demand for better understanding of environmental pollution problems through wider pollution monitoring [19] in participatory sensing mode. In this line, the present work aim to develop a participatory sensing device for dust pollution monitoring and develop a reflective activity around the tool.

2.2 Background

Dramatic cost reduction with improved specifications in mobile computers and micro controllers facilitates a great leap in with participatory sensing . Currently, there is a proliferation of participatory activities which focuses on environmental monitoring enabled with games directed towards formal and informal education and awareness [20].

This review [20] gives a extensive survey on participatory sensing in different domains. Applications of participatory sensing in domains such as health and fitness, environmental monitoring, transportation and civil infrastructure and urban sensing were discussed. In environmental monitoring domain air pollutants such as Carbon dioxide, Carbon monoxide, temperate, relative humidity, combustible gases [21] and Ozone [22]were deployed in participatory sensing mode.

2.3 Activity Overview

It is comprised of sensing outdoor particulate pollution level using a hand held tablet computer connected with a dust sensor device. The activity revolves around reflecting participants field activity experience with dust pollutant readings from the device.

2.4 Activity code

The activity developed based on Android tablet computer, Arduino micro controller, Blue tooth shield and Grove dust sensor. The program provides a serial data communication between Dust sensor connected with micro controller and Android tablet by

blue tooth communication between them. Terminal blue tooth serial reading software in Android tablet converts the transferred data from micro controller and gives its output in readable format. The complete source code of the activity which is in open source domain is hosted in <https://github.com/nishadhka/Nudge>. Full source code of this activity can be downloaded from this link.

2.5 Nudge: Features and program

2.5.1 Feature overview

Nudge activity revolves around a participatory sensing tool developed in Android tablet. The tool has features to monitor particulate pollution/dust concentration using a low cost dust sensor (Ref. Figure 2.1 and table 2.1). Bluetooth shield is an add-on module for Arduino microcontroller. Three pins of dust sensors were connected to the Bluetooth shield which was mounted with Arduino board. Arduino is powered by USB battery pack. By Arduino Integrated Development Environment, sensor values are read in Android Bluetooth serial terminal application (Figs.2.2 and 2.3)

FIGURE 2.1: Components in Android tablet based dust sensing device

2.5.2 Features

2.5.3 Program

The program was written in Arduino IDE and it was a compilation of two sample programs dealing with Dust sensor [23] and blue tooth serial [24] communication. The

Date	Item	Vendor	Quantity	Price in INR
19/06/2013	USB-Battery pack-1000mAh	ProtoCentral-Bangalore	1	1799
19/06/2013	Grove Bluetooth Shield	ProtoCentral-Bangalore	1	1299
18/06/2013	Grove Dust sensor	ProtoCentral-Bangalore	1	1612
10/06/2013	Arduino board	Kaveri electronics-Coimbatore	1	1835
19/06/2013	Laser cutting and Acrylic box	Local shop	1	100
19/06/2013	Ribbon	Local shop	1	10
			Total	6655

TABLE 2.1: Particulars used in Android tablet based dust sensing device

FIGURE 2.2: Android phone based dust sensing device

FIGURE 2.3: Transferring of dust concentration data from 'Arduino' to 'Android' in Blue tooth serial app

following codes were used to communicate Arduino sensor reading to Android serial reading application.

```
/*  
DUST sensor- blue tooth communication  
Program by Nishadh.K.A.
```

Compilation of

```
Grove - Dust Sensor Demo v1.0  
Interface to Shinyei Model PPD42NS Particle Sensor  
Program by Christopher Nafis  
Written April 2012
```

and

BluetoothShield Demo Code Slave.pde. This sketch could be used with Master.pde to establish connection between two Arduino. It can also be used for one slave bluetooth connected by the device(PC/Smart Phone) with bluetooth function.

2011 Copyright (c) Seeed Technology Inc. All right reserved.

Author: Steve Chang

This demo code is free software; you can redistribute it and/or modify it under the terms of the GNU Lesser General Public License as published by the Free Software Foundation; either version 2.1 of the License, or (at your option) any later version.

```
JST Pin 1 (Black Wire) => Arduino GND  
JST Pin 3 (Red wire)   => Arduino 5VDC  
JST Pin 4 (Yellow wire) => Arduino Digital Pin 8  
*/
```

```
int pin = 8;  
unsigned long duration;  
unsigned long starttime;  
unsigned long samptime_ms = 30000;//sampe 30s ;  
unsigned long lowpulseoccupancy = 0;
```

```
float ratio = 0;
float concentration = 0;
#include <SoftwareSerial.h> //Software Serial Port
#define RxD 2
#define TxD 3
#define DEBUG_ENABLED 1
SoftwareSerial blueToothSerial(RxD,TxD);

void setup()
{
    Serial.begin(9600);
    pinMode(RxD, INPUT);
    pinMode(TxD, OUTPUT);
    setupBlueToothConnection();
    pinMode(8,INPUT);
    starttime = millis();//get the current time;
}

float getDust()
{
    duration = pulseIn(pin, LOW);
    lowpulseoccupancy = lowpulseoccupancy+duration;

    if ((millis()-starttime) > sampletime_ms)//if the sampel time == 30s
    {
        ratio = lowpulseoccupancy/(sampletime_ms*10.0);
        concentration = 1.1*pow(ratio,3)-3.8*pow(ratio,2)+520*ratio+0.62;
        Serial.print(lowpulseoccupancy);
        Serial.print(",");
        Serial.print(ratio);
        Serial.print(",");
        Serial.println(concentration);
        lowpulseoccupancy = 0;
        starttime = millis();

        return (float)concentration;
    }
}
```

```
void loop()
{

    char recvChar;
    while(1)
    {
        if(blueToothSerial.available())
        {
            recvChar = blueToothSerial.read();
            Serial.print(recvChar);

            if(recvChar == 't' || recvChar == 'T')
            {
                blueToothSerial.print("Dust concentration: ");
                blueToothSerial.println(getDust());
            }
        }
        if(Serial.available())
        {
            recvChar = Serial.read();
            blueToothSerial.print(recvChar);
        }
    }

}

void setupBlueToothConnection()
{
    blueToothSerial.begin(38400);
    blueToothSerial.print("\r\n+STWMOD=0\r\n");
    blueToothSerial.print("\r\n+STNA=SeeedBTSlave\r\n");
    blueToothSerial.print("\r\n+STOAUT=1\r\n");
    blueToothSerial.print("\r\n+STAUTO=0\r\n");
    delay(2000);
}
```

2.6 Conclusion

A portable particulate matter/dust pollution monitoring device was prototyped. Its further development in terms of linking with map and pollution visualization can provide tools in participatory sensing activity.

Appendix A

Chipko wetlands (Hug the wetlands)- a game for adaptation thinking in urban area -proposal

This proposal was submitted in a global climate change related proposal competition conducted by MIT Climate CoLab www.climatecolab.org and was selected for final round of competition[25]

A.1 Introduction

Sea level rise, increased Flood or drought frequency and intensity are the major climate change risks faced by urban areas [26],[27]. Normally wetland systems including rivers, lakes, marshes, and coastal areas are basic infrastructures alleviating these problems[28] [29]. So any enhancement in terms of better management, planning of these resources related with urban areas will be a adaptive solution and driver to make cities more resilient against climate change.

This proposal is intended to create awareness on this relationship of cities and wetland systems by making a virtual globe based simulation game, Chipko wetlands. The game challenges players to embrace wetland systems against simulated climate change scenarios in virtual globe (Such as Bhuvan, Google Earth, World Wind etc) to make their chosen urban area more resilient. The aim of the proposal is to blend the problem solving and motivations of play, to generate interest on the game task and to make it as an important awareness creation, collective problem solving tool [10] [9]. By systematically organizing and popularizing the game and its developments among youngsters,

this proposal intends to popularize the wetland systems based adaptation thinking and in the long run to improve the game to make it as a crowd backed collective intelligent planning and management tool for urban leaders and officials.

A.2 Game overview

The game comprised of five steps, which will be running for 15 days duration in virtual globe (Fig.A.1).

FIGURE A.1: Steps in Chipko wetlands games

- Choose city: The city where player residing or his/her favorite, the boundary will be the urban administrative boundary.
- Demarcate wetlands: Every urban area is dependent of fresh water source and drainage facility. Wetland systems are catering these needs. Players have to demarcate these systems (Chipko wetlands/Hug the wetlands). It will be of catchment (rivers/streams, lakes etc) demarcation.
- Model the system: Using the various prebuilt models (viz., DEM, sewer system model, ground water simulation models, Runoff models, Sea level rise models) players have to create composite 3D representation of wetland systems in their urban area. This will be a important step, since this determines the adaptation or resilience of players urban area against various climate change scenarios.

- Test the model: This step is to make sure the created model is adapting to eventualities of climate change scenario by experimenting with various intense scenarios of flood, drought or sea level rise. Up to this the game play duration is for 10 days.
- Play simulations: After the four steps of model creation and experimentation, players have to expose their city wetland system modeled infrastructure with climate change scenarios. In this step player will not have any control over the simulation. In this step, game duration is for 5 days and in which a total of 100 years of different projected climate change scenario will be running in virtual globe. The player task is to manage his/her urban area under this various climate change scenario and if needed to create new models or infrastructures to make it adaptive.

A.3 Development feasibility

Chipko wetland will be developed as a web client playable in web browser in which the virtual globe satellite view is set to be the base theme and all the 3D models and simulation will be added to this base as a layer stack in a Web Geographical Information System (Web GIS) platform.

- For Step1:

Choosing a favorite urban area by player will be the game trigger and it will make the game software application to set the Area of Interest (AOI) in the underlying game WebGIS platform. The Urban area administrative boundary will be from readily available GIS vector file format such as ESRI Shape file or kml.
- For Step2:

Demarcation of wetland systems by player is basically drawing of polygon shape in Web GIS platform. Demarcation of wetland systems such as rivers, lakes or coastal area will be assessed by the recent Land Use, Land Cover (LULC) map of the AOI. In which the wetland class of the LULC map will be checked with the demarcated area. It will be again cross checked with the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) of the AOI. DEM of the AOI will be also used for creating the models in step 3.
- For Step3:

The modeling step comprised of physical system modeling and system functional modeling.

The physical system modeling is based on DEM and shape file format of the urban area street map, wetland system catchment will be modeled using DEM and urban area street map will be used for modeling the sewerage system in the urban area, which will be used for flood simulations. Creation of sewerage system model from road network is by a simple assumption of it from historical building of sewers parallel to the road network. The data for road network will be used from open street map.

The wetland systems' functional modeling will be carried out using the numerical models on various wetlands system processes. Free statistical software packages written using R will be used for this purposes. For hydrological modeling hydromad R package and for ground water modeling R-Groundwater will be used. For use with gaming, R packages will be ported with scripting languages to make the calculations based on players requirement in the game application. For adding the geo-spatial element in the modeling result all the models will be tried to run in geogrids preferably 30 m resolutions to sync with DEM's geogrid resolution.

This step is the most complex and difficult step in game development, majority of the game development time will be devoted to research on this. For this step open source 3D game engines like DELTA 3D or pre build 3D objects such as Google's Sketchup which can be visualized in virtual globe will be explored. Usability of open source empire-building game Freeciv will also be explored. The game engines are used to create the virtual environment to simulate the flood or other climate change causalities in the game application. The Freeciv will be considered as the model for developing the Chipko wetlands.

- For step 4 and 5:

Both these steps are involving running of climate change scenario simulations on the developed model in chosen AOI or player urban area. IPCC fourth assessment based climate predictions simulation such as Google Earth Climate change simulations supplied as KMZ file format or more advanced modeling framework such as Radically Open Modeling Architecture used in Climate Colab will be explored to use in this step[30].

To get help on the game development, real world problem solving game developer community such as Gameful (www.gameful.org) will be contacted.

A.4 Expected Outcomes

- Planning and training tool[31] [32]:

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- Games are increasingly used as a training module in different sectors. By field validation, the Chipko module can be made into a adaptation planning and management tool for urban leaders and officials.
 - Resource Monitoring and legal actions: The game can be act as an resource monitoring tool. The virtual globe satellite imageries are updated frequently and it also shows the archived imageries, which can be act as mechanical turk based monitoring of the earth surface emphasizing the wetland systems. It gives further opportunity to take legal action with monitoring evidence against encroacher.
 - It can give tools for generating new ecological engineering options which can be simulated in the game console and have deliberation of the stakeholders to try it out in the field.

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